

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT
AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY OF CONTAINMENT IN
UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

The article emphasizes the scientific and theoretical aspects of modernizing the economy, technologically and technologically updating production, strengthening the impact of industrial production in socio-economic development while maintaining existing industrial potential in our country, expanding its capabilities in accelerating the reproduction process.

Keywords: theory, system, technological policy, process technologies, classroom, region, industry, innovation, innovative approach, innovative park, innovative infrastructure.

Introduction

The radical transformation of Uzbekistan's national economy, the step-by-step development of the industrial sector's global competitiveness, the saturation of the domestic market with national industrial products, and the sequential mastery of export-oriented goods production necessitate, on the one hand, finding scientific and theoretical solutions to these issues and, on the other hand, developing an optimal industrialization strategy based on global industrialization experiences.

In this industrialization strategy, the effective utilization of state foreign trade policies, the improvement of the investment and construction complex, and the efficient use of the tools of tax, customs, and regional development policies play a decisive role.

It is worth noting that the policy of industrializing national production encompasses not only measures to stimulate economic, financial, organizational, legal, and technical-innovative processes in the industrial sector and to create conditions for fully mobilizing the private sector's potential in this process but also requires supporting the integration of industry with other economic sectors. Additionally, the social and environmental aspects of industrialization are also pertinent.

From this perspective, the process of industrialization and the state policy on industrialization urgently call for the systematic scientific and theoretical study of these processes, the enrichment of their methodological aspects, and the improvement of the institutional foundations for the practical implementation of industrialization policy.

Research methodology

The scientific and theoretical foundations of industrialization policy encompass theoretical perspectives, ideas, approaches, and methodological research dedicated to the industrialization process, state industrialization policy, intersectoral integration, including agro-industrial integration, the placement of industrial sectors, and the management and acceleration of urbanization. Additionally, scientific studies focused on investments, their management, the regulation of investment flows, and the determination of investment efficiency can also be included in these foundations.

In some of these areas, our country has undertaken substantial and comprehensive research and monographic works. However, there has not been systematic research on managing the industrialization process, expanding its scope, enhancing the participation of the private sector in these processes, and managing the interlinked processes of industrialization and urbanization.

Promoting and organizing scientific and methodological research in this field will improve industrialization policy, expand the scientific, technical, and innovative foundations of the national economy, and enhance the understanding of complex and contradictory issues in industrial development.

The essence of the industrialization process is characterized by the rapid integration of the industrial sector into all branches of the economy, particularly agriculture and services, through the widespread introduction of machinery and technology into production processes. To accelerate the industrialization process, it is essential to expand the socio-economic, educational, and scientific-technical foundations within the country.

In the future, the industrialization process will not only play a crucial role in ensuring the material and technical development of other economic sectors but will also embody significant scientific and technological achievements and foster the accumulation of knowledge-intensive investments.

the following key changes are expected to drive the rapid development of the industrialization process:

-the influence of globalization on industrial enterprises will intensify as a result of the efficient functioning of markets, leading to an improved environment for private entrepreneurship and enhanced corporate governance.

-the decline in costs for computers, communication, and transportation, along with the liberalization of trade and investment, will accelerate.

-the impact of universal technologies, particularly those based on information technology, will increase, potentially spreading across all sectors of the economy and branches of industry.

-the importance of small and private entrepreneurial firms in the knowledge-intensive industry will grow, contributing more significantly to economic growth, job creation, and rising incomes.

-the emergence and growth of new, modern sectors and production areas, alongside the replacement of sectors with sharply declining efficiency, will form the basis of structural shifts in industry and underpin robust economic growth.

The experience of numerous countries demonstrates that the initial stages of industrial development often focus on the rapid advancement of agricultural and mining raw material processing sectors. In an industrialized society, the processing industry itself is significantly enhanced through information technology. During the industrialization process, large private corporations emerge, becoming a hallmark of an industrialized society.

At the advanced stages of development, it is logical to assert that the balance between the production of consumer goods and investment sector products becomes more equitable. Global experience indicates that it is not necessary for all countries to pass through every stage of industrial development to achieve industrialization. Currently, a group of Southeast Asian countries, without heavy industry sectors, have highly specialized in the production of information technology, generating substantial revenues in this field.

The deepening of international labor division and regional integration is leading to an increasingly integrated global economy, where national economies become inseparable parts. This necessitates a reevaluation of industrial development issues from a different perspective under new conditions.

This involves improving the structural composition of industry, enhancing the economic activity of industrial enterprises, privatizing industrial enterprises, establishing import-substituting industries, and orienting towards export, all within the framework of industrial policy. The industrialization policy, in the context of globalization, aims to enhance the competitiveness of the economy by

promoting private entrepreneurship, encompassing broader objectives than the development of specific sectors or industries.

As a result of this policy, the opportunities to leverage comparative advantages in the economy will expand, and high-tech production will be mastered.

Results and discussion

From the perspective of foreign trade strategies, industrialization policy aims to enhance export potential and substitute imports by implementing deep structural changes in production through the efficient use of existing capacities. Increasing export potential and local industrialists mastering the production of import-substituting goods are fundamental aspects of industrialization and key objectives of industrialization policy.

The role of industrialization policy in the industrialization process is linked to three principles of state structural policy: facilitating and creating conditions for economic efficiency, enabling economic agents to coordinate their activities, and ensuring an increase in overall economic activity within society.

Industrialization policy can be categorized based on its targeted objectives as follows:

-General Industrialization Policy (GIP): This involves macroeconomic measures aimed at creating equal conditions for all industrial sectors through macroeconomic tools and levers.

-Specific Sector Industrial Policy (SSIP): Here, the state establishes a system of incentives specifically for the development of industrial sectors. However, this approach may lead to potential disadvantages for other sectors, such as agriculture.

-Industrial Specialization Policy (ISP): This focuses on prioritizing the development of certain industrial sectors while allowing other sectors to develop under general conditions.

-Firm-Specific Industrial Policy (FSIP): Based on socio-economic significance or foreign partnerships, this involves the development of state policies for specific enterprises or projects. Examples include implementing special programs for adopting new technologies or producing new products.

For transitional economies entering a new phase of industrialization, one or more of these approaches may form the structural components of industrialization policy.

To accelerate the pace of industrialization, the state implements a specialized policy for the industrialization of national production. This includes

the improvement of the industrial structure. The initial industrialization policy of the state should be aligned with the development level of the industrial sectors within the national economy.

It is logical to establish a strategy based on the country's material and intellectual potential, subsequently transitioning to the full utilization of intensive factors of industrialization.

Industrialization policy primarily comprises a set of measures aimed at the structural reconstruction of the economy, the establishment and development of vital industrial sectors within a specific country. However, the state's role in accelerating the industrialization process extends beyond this; it also involves the development of production infrastructure and the creation of an intellectual foundation to manage and innovate industrial production.

In his work "Report on Manufacturers," American statesman Alexander Hamilton emphasized the importance of industrialization and industrial policy, arguing that when serious threats to the national economy arise, the most effective way for the state to mitigate these threats is by protecting the national market and industry. From that period to the present, the general reasons for pursuing industrialization policies in industrializing countries can be summarized as follows:

- The transition from traditional to new sectors faces obstacles due to insufficient inclination of producers towards innovation.

- Many entrepreneurs fear failure, resulting in a scarcity of risk-takers.

- New industrial enterprises may lack the competitive strength to survive in the global market, facing the risk of being "strangled in the cradle."

Other countries consistently support their national industrialists with material and financial aid from the state, leading to unequal and unfair competition in the global market.

Conclusions

Summarizing the above considerations, industrialization in the context of globalization refers to the economic and technological process whereby national economies continuously enhance their competitiveness in the global economy. This is achieved through the rapid development of industrial sectors based on comparative advantage and advanced technology, driven by both the private sector and the state, and the widespread application of scientific and technological advancements across all areas.

The complexity of the industrialization process lies in its demand for active participation in the international division of labor under conditions of

intense global market competition. In other words, a country's ability to industrialize is closely linked to its capacity to produce export-oriented goods and services.

It is evident that industrialization has become a vital necessity for all countries today. The "endless competitive environment" and the rapidly increasing interconnectedness in the global economy compel countries to modernize their national industries and swiftly adopt innovative development pathways. This is crucial for improving the conditions for industrial modernization and achieving rapid, innovation-driven growth

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